

Growth of Indian Banking Sector: Emerging Trends

Dr. Naveen Agrawal¹, Prachi Arya²

¹Assistant Professor, Faculty of Commerce, K.R.P.G. College, Mathura,

²(Research Scholar), K.R.P.G. college, Mathura

Corresponding Author- Dr. Naveen Agrawal

Email- drnaveenagralkrc@gmail.com

Abstract: 'Changes are law of nature.' Banking sector is fundamental part of economy. Every change brings some opportunities and challenges. To cash opportunities and to make challenge in opportunities build banking sector much stronger we need to find out recent changes. The objective of the study to find out theoretical aspect of recent changes in Indian banking sector through analysis of newspaper articles, research papers, reports etc.

High credit growth, increasing digital transactions, use of modern AI technologies, decreasing Non- performing assets comes as opportunities in Indian banking sector whereas increasing interest rates due to inflation; and cyber security comes as challenges in future.

Keywords: Banking sector, growth, trends

Introduction:

The bank is known as such institution which accepts deposits and lends loans and provides other finance related services. Banking has defined in Banking Regulation Act 1949; Section 5(b) as a business which:

1. Accepts deposits of money from public.
2. For purpose of accepting deposits: Lending, Investing.
3. Deposits will be repayable on demand or otherwise.
4. Withdrawal of money by cheque, draft, order or otherwise.

The activities carried out by banks known as **Banking Activities**. Now banks provide retail services like E Banking, Net Banking, Mobile banking, Debit & Credit card , A.T.M.(Automatic Teller Machine) and so on which help the people provide banking services anytime, anywhere .

The bank is an active performer in financial market. Supply of money in circulation is largely controlled by banks. Banks can influence nature and characteristics of production of the country thereby, it can be helpful in improvising the economic situation of country. Now banks have become fundamental part of worlds' economic development.

In the current scenario of extreme global uncertainty, Indian banking sector able to with stand in severe regressed situations such as Silicon Valley bank crisis, Russia-Ukraine war, Covid -19. Due to recent changes in banking sector of India, banks are able to fight back and make a strong comeback. They are profitable, liquidate, and growing day by day. In the research I will discuss about the different changes in current Indian banking scenario and try to find out why they are growing in spite of global upside down situations.

Literature Review:

A Literature Review is reading, analyzing, researching, evaluating and summarizing scholarly literature about a specific topic and being able to

provide conclusion about result and methods. A Literature Review is a detailed and critical inspection of scholarly research papers, articles, books, and other sources relevant to a particular issue, area of research or theory; by providing a description, summary, and critical evaluation of each work.

Sidhu et al. (2022)⁹. Focused on impact of Liquidity Coverage Ratio on performance of selected Indian bank. The research investigates the relation of liquidity and financial performance .The secondary data collected from the Reserve Bank of India and Centre for Monitoring Indian Economy's Prowess database for the study. Banks' profitability variables was Net Profit Margin (NIM) return variable was Return on Assets(R.O.A.) bank risk calculated through Net Profitable Assets (NPA) .Data analysis made through descriptive statistics, correlation and dynamic panel data analysis. The study reveals that increase in Liquidity Coverage Ratio and its components increase the funding cost and have adverse effect on financial performance of banks.

Pierri, N. & Timmer,Y. (2022)⁸ did an investigation on importance of technology during crisis. The study conducted on United States banks. The study reveals enhanced role of adoption of information technology on banks' profitability during crisis.

Anitha et al. (2022)³. Did an empirical study on factors affect the financial performance of selected commercial banks of India. Total four banks taken for data analysis and data collected from Reserve Bank of India for the period of ten years. Factors analysis and regression analysis used for data analysis. The study reported that financial performance is affected by profitability ratios which were higher for the banks of private sector.

Agrwala,V. & Agrwala ,N.(2019)¹ Did a critical review on non-performing assets in the Indian banking industry. The purpose of this study is

to look into NPAs growth pattern during the period 2010-2017. The private sector banks, the nationalized banks and SBI and its associates have been considered as sample. Statistical tool geometric mean used for data analysis. Results of the study shows that private sector banks growth rate of NPAs is low as compared to the nationalized banks, as well as the SBI and its associates.

Abbasov et al (2019)² conducted a study on digitalization in banking sector. The study examined major trends in development of digital banking sector in Azerbaijan. The study used general scientific method to analysis trends in digital banking. The study reveals progress of mobile banking and internet banking is closely related to the development of e commerce.

Soni, V (2019)¹⁰ did a study about role of artificial intelligence in combating cyber threats and cybercrimes in banking. Various opportunities are provided by AI techniques, which help the banking sector to increase prosperity and growth. In the paper different kind of advantage and disadvantage in adoption of Artificial intelligence are discussed.

Gizaw et al (2015)⁶ conducted study on the impact of credit risk on profitability performance of commercial banks in Ethiopia. The sample was collected from eight commercial banks of Ethiopia during twelve years 2001-2012. Descriptive analysis and panel data regression analysis done through (STATA Version 11) software. The study reveals need of enhancing credit risk management for better profitability.

Aspal, et al (2014)⁴ did an empirical analysis of capital adequacy in the Indian private sector banks. The study aims to find out bank variables have an impact on capital adequacy ratio in Indian private sector banks during 2008-2012. Twenty private sector banks of India have been considered as sample. Statistical tool multiple linear regression analysis used for data analysis. The study shows that the private sector banks of India manage a higher level of capital reserve than prescribed by Reserve Bank of India. The study also found that Indian private sector banks have excess funds to meet their requirements and have opportunity to give more advances to public by protecting owner's shares.

Malik et al (2014)⁷ did a study about interest rate and its effect on bank's profitability. The study conducted to check and examine the market interest rate effect on the bank's profitability in public and private sectors of Pakistan. The sample of the study was divided into two categories. 1) Public sector banks: which includes four nationalized banks and 2) Private sector banks: which includes six private sector banks of Pakistan during 2008-2012? The study concluded that the interest rate affects both sector banks significantly.

Private sector banks had more effect as compared to public sector banks.

Bohaene et al (2012)⁵ conducted a study about relationship between credit risk and profitability of banks. The sample of the study was taken six commercial banks of Ghana for the period 2005-2009. Analysis of data made through regression, descriptive statistics, variance of inflation factor analysis. The result of the study revealed that the credit risk had positive and significant effect on bank's profitability.

Research Methodology:

Research methodology is a master plan that specifies the need and procedure for gathering and analyzing the information required. "It involves various steps that are generally followed by a researcher in studying his research problem along with the logic behind the" (Bajpai, Naval 2013). "A research design is the arrangement of conditions for collection and analysis of data in a manner that aims to combine relevance to the research purpose with economy in procedure." (Kothari, 2004). The following research is descriptive in nature. Source of data will be secondary. The major sources of secondary data are:

1. Report on Trend and Progress of Banking in India
2. Reserve Bank of India Publications

Besides this, government reports, several books, newspaper articles, websites, online research papers available in Google scholar studied to obtain the desired information.

Objective: This research aims to know about recent changes in Indian Banking sector.

Findings:

1. **Declining Non Performing Assets:** Gross non-performing assets (GNPA) declined to 5.8 %; says 'Trends and Progress of Banking in India' report of financial year 2022 from its peak during year 2018 which means a better assets quality. Reduction in outstanding GNPA's made through write-offs, recoveries and lower slippages.
2. **Higher Liquidity Coverage:** Indian banks are performing better in the term of liquidity with the ratio of 135.6% (it should be 100%). whereas global economy confronted with serious financial stability challenges due to recent liquidity crisis in the banking sector in some advanced economy.
3. **Better Capital Position:** Indian banks capital position has been improved. The banks should meet the minimum regulatory capital requirements regulated by Reserve Bank of India even in severe stress situations so banks have enough capital buffers to have better capital position.

4. **Rising Interest Rates:** Due to Russia-Ukraine war inflation increased all over the world, India also had this inflationary stress, to control the situation Reserve Bank of India had to increase interest rates.
 5. **Growth of Credit:** Credit growth reached 17.5% in December 2022 which was highest in past several years we are getting single digits. Public sector banks will be able to compete to Private sector banks due to credit growth.
 6. **Digital Economy:** India is now developing as digital economy, as part of **Digital India** campaign, after covid 19 which made people realized digital payments are easier to use and free from any physical appearance in bank branches that saves time and cost.
 7. **Cyber Security:** Increasing digital payments whereas providing better growth in economy but leads to many cyber frauds related to cyber crime. Cyber security and educate consumers towards safe digital banking are main concern in India.
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